

Original Article

Evaluation of Properties of Heat-cure Denture Base Materials Incorporated with Nanodiamonds

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Despite their weak mechanical properties, heat-cure acrylic materials are frequently employed to produce removable dental prostheses. This study was aimed to evaluate the effect of incorporating different concentrations (0.00wt%, 0.50 wt%, 1.00 wt%, and 2.00wt%) of nanodiamonds on the properties of heat-cure denture base resin materials. A total of 480 specimens, which comprises 160 specimens from each denture base material, were fabricated using the conventional compression molding technique. Forty specimens were allocated to evaluate each property with 10 specimens (n=10) in each concentration of the denture base resin and Nanodiamond composite. The specimens were subjected to evaluate flexural strength, impact strength, surface hardness, water sorption and solubility. The obtained data were subjected to statistical analysis using One-way ANOVA followed by Posthoc analysis. The specimens modified with 0.50wt% exhibited the maximum flexural strength compared to other groups. The impact strength was reduced in the modified groups compared to the unmodified group. The microhardness, water sorption, and solubility were increased as the concentration of nanodiamonds increased. One-way ANOVA showed significant ($p=0.000$) differences among the groups at various concentrations. Incorporation of lower concentrations of Nanodiamonds into denture base materials may enhance the mechanical properties.

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Introduction

Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) resin is the current material of choice for denture base fabrication, because of its favorable working characteristics, accurate fit and stability in the oral environment, superior aesthetics, and inexpensive processing equipment usage [1]. Despite these beneficial properties, it has few drawbacks; including frequent fracture due to fatigue, chemical degradation of the base material, low thermal conductivity [2], and ease of microbial adhesion to the intaglio surface [3]. To overcome these shortcomings, various modifications of PMMA have been attempted [4,5]. Attempts to improve the strength by reinforcing them with several fibers exhibited varying success [2,5-7].

Particulates (Fillers) are another type of reinforcement in polymer-based composite materials [8-11]. Each particulate filler type has

different properties, and these, in turn, are influenced by the particle size, shape, and surface chemistry. Particle-specific surface area and packing are critical aspects to impart mechanical properties. Further, filler loading is also an essential factor that influences the mechanical properties of resin materials. The principal filler types include natural mineral fillers and synthetic mineral fillers. Filler surface modification is an important characteristic for providing a strong bond between the resin matrix and the filler particles. Most particulate fillers investigated were in micrometer size, inorganic, and polar which can give rise to poor compatibility with the hydrocarbon polymers resulting in weakening of the polymer structures [8-10].

Nanoparticles (NPs) are currently gaining popularity as starting points for the development of functional devices. These particles are being studied for their interesting physical properties that differ from those of the bulk phase. Small diameters and a high surface/volume ratio are responsible for their improved properties [12]. Several metallic and non-metallic nanoparticles, such as TiO₂, Al₂O₃, and ZrO₂, have received considerable attention. These

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nanoparticles have recently been used to improve the mechanical strength of denture base materials, with varying degrees of success [13-17].

Biomedical uses of carbon nanomaterials have evolved because of recent advances in nanoscience and nanotechnology and are currently undergoing extensive research. In this context, carbon nanotubes have been experimented with for modifying the strength of denture base resin materials. However, these attempts have not been successful [18]. Nanodiamonds (ND) are a relatively new family of carbon-based nanomaterials with a nanometer-scale diamond structure. NDs inherit most of the superior properties of bulk diamonds and deliver them at the nanoscale [19]. These properties include superior hardness and young's modulus, biocompatibility, optical properties and fluorescence, high thermal conductivity, and chemical stability [20]. Numerous applications of NDs have been explored in nanomedicine for drug delivery applications, biomedical imaging, and biosensors [18]. In addition, they have been used for protein immobilization, bio purification, and bioseparation [20]. However, the applications of NDs have not been explored in dentistry. A very few studies have been conducted on the antifungal activity, surface characteristics and physical properties of PMMA-based denture base materials incorporated with NDs [21,22]. Only two studies [23, 24] have investigated the mechanical properties of denture base materials incorporated with NDs, with varying results. Therefore, this study was designed to evaluate the effect of NDs incorporation on the mechanical and physical properties of denture base materials.

Materials and Methods

Three heat-cure denture base materials, Trevlon (Dentsply India Pvt. Ltd, India), TriplexHot (Ivoclar Vivadent, USA), and DPI heat-cure (Dental Products of India, India), were modified with various concentrations of diamond nanopowder (Nanostructured & Amorphous Materials, Inc., USA).

Preparation of acrylic specimens

A total of 480 specimens, which comprises 160 specimens from each denture base material, were fabricated using the conventional compression molding technique. The samples size was calculated using G power 3.1 software. Acrylic specimens were fabricated following ADA specification number 12 by investing metal strips of 65 x 10 x 3 mm, 50 x 6 x 4 mm, and 20x 2 mm for the evaluation of flexural strength, impact strength, surface hardness, respectively, and metal discs of 50 x 2.5 mm for measuring water sorption and solubility. Metal strips and discs were carefully removed after the investment material was set and a thin layer of separating medium was applied in the mold space. The nanodiamonds were added to the monomer liquid at different concentrations, 0.50wt%, 1.00wt%, and 2.00wt%, and stirred thoroughly using the glass rod for uniform dispersion of NDs. With no addition of NDs to the monomer were considered as the control/unmodified group. Denture base materials with various concentrations of the NDs were considered as modified groups. Denture base acrylic powder and monomer liquid with NDs were mixed as per the manufacturer's recommendations and packed into the mold when the mix reached the dough consistency. The flask was closed and kept under pressure using hydraulic press apparatus followed by bench curing for 30 minutes. Then the flask was tightly secured in a clamp and transferred into a thermostatically controlled water bath (Acrylizer, Confident A-73, India), and cured as per the manufacturer's recommendations. The temperature of the water bath was increased to 73 ± 1°C within 30 minutes and maintained for 90 minutes. The temperature was raised to 100°C and maintained for 60 minutes. The flask was allowed to cool in the

water bath to room temperature. the acrylic resin specimens were retrieved after deflasking. The specimen were finished and polished conventionally.

Among 160 specimens from each denture base material, 40 specimens are allocated to evaluate each test. Each concentration group (control, 0.50wt%, 1.00wt%, and 2.00wt%) received ten specimens (n=10) from a total of forty specimens.

Evaluation of flexural strength

The flexural strength was evaluated using a three-point bending test on a computerized universal testing machine (Instron 8801, United Kingdom) at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/minute. The load was applied until the specimen fractured from which the flexural strength value was computed automatically by the machine.

Evaluation of impact strength

The samples were subjected to impact forces using the IZOD type of impact tester (KRYSTAL Industries, India). A notch of 1.2 mm was made at the mid-point of the specimens using a carborundum disc to avoid brittle fracture. The sample was placed in a metal fixture so that the middle of the sample coincided with the striking pendulum. The pendulum struck the sample and resulting in fracture. The energy required to break the sample was measured in Joules/mm².

Evaluation of microhardness

The microhardness was measured using Vickers hardness test apparatus (Daksh Quality Systems Pvt Ltd., India) with a diamond pyramid indenter. A load of 25 gm was applied at 25 seconds dwelling time on the specimens resulting in the formation of a square indentation. A total of five indentations were made at different points for each specimen, and the means of individual specimens were averaged. The readouts of the lengths of the diagonals were immediately taken after each indentation, allowing a minimal (as short as 10 seconds) time interval to elapse between making and reading the indentations to avoid the viscoelastic recovery of the diagonals after indentation.

Evaluation of water sorption and solubility

The specimens were placed in glass vessels, which were desiccated at 37 ± 1°C in a vacuum oven for 24 h (Asian Test Equipments, India). Then the specimens were removed from the oven and left at room temperature for 2 hours, which completed a 24-h cycle. The discs were weighed daily using an analytical balance (Wensar, India) to record 24-h weighing cycles. The complete cycle was repeated until a constant mass (M1) was obtained, i.e., until the mass loss for each specimen was not more than 0.1 mg per 24-h cycle. Thereafter, the specimens were placed back in their labeled vessels, and 15 mL of deionized water (W) were added using manual pipettes. The vessels were sealed, brought back into the oven, and kept at 37 ± 1°C for 7 days. All the vessels were removed from the oven and kept at room temperature for 2 hours. The specimens were dried with absorbent paper for 15s. They were then weighed again to obtain M2. After weighting, the specimens were reconditioned in the desiccators until they reached a constant weight (M3) using the cycle described for M1. The values for water sorption (Wsp) and solubility (Wsl) in micrograms per cubic millimeter were calculated using the following equations:

$$W_{sp} = (M2-M1)/V \text{ and } W_{sl} = (M1-M3)/V$$

Results

The mean and standard deviations for mechanical and physical

Table 1: Flexural Strength, Impact strength and Vickers hardness of three denture base materials incorporated with various concentrations of nanodiamonds (One-way ANOVA)

Material	Concentration of Nanodiamonds	N	Flexural Strength (MPa)		Impact Strength (KJ/mm ²)		Surface Hardness (Kg/mm ²)	
			Mean ± SD	p	Mean ± SD		Mean±SD	p
Trevlon	0.00%	30	105.60 ± 7.32	0.001	4.50 ± 0.30	0.001	14.55 ± 0.77	0.001
	0.50%	30	120.97 ± 9.93		4.31 ± 0.26		21.03 ± 1.45	
	1.00%	30	101.31 ± 6.70		4.20 ± 0.29		22.67 ± 1.39	
	2.00%	30	93.20 ± 5.50		3.95 ± 0.18		24.01 ± 1.14	
TriplexHot	0.00%	30	80.02 ± 8.46	0.000	4.27 ± 0.27	0.001	17.45 ± 0.63	0.001
	0.50%	30	88.43 ± 5.12		4.18 ± 0.30		22.54 ± 1.52	
	1.00%	30	76.38 ± 5.63		3.98 ± 0.28		23.91 ± 1.85	
	2.00%	30	69.09 ± 3.79		3.78 ± 0.21		24.60 ± 1.94	
DPI	0.00%	30	79.65 ± 9.25	0.001	3.47 ± 0.34	0.001	16.89 ± 2.11	0.001
	0.50%	30	91.25 ± 8.17		3.24 ± 0.23		20.33 ± 1.83	
	1.00%	30	75.89 ± 4.70		3.14 ± 0.17		22.04 ± 2.05	
	2.00%	30	68.81 ± 4.31		2.96 ± 0.17		24.24 ± 1.57	

properties of unmodified and modified denture base materials are given in tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Flexural Strength

The flexural strength of the three denture base materials containing 0.50wt% NDs was the highest. The flexural strength of denture base materials was shown to decrease as the concentration of NDs increased. One-way ANOVA showed a significant difference ($p=0.000$) in the flexural strength within the denture base materials (table 1).

In post hoc analysis, Trevlon and DPI denture base materials incorporated with 0.50wt% of NDs exhibited significant differences ($p=0.000$) with the remaining concentrations. Also, the control group of Trevlon and DPI materials showed a significant difference ($p=0.004$, $p=0.007$, respectively) with 2.00wt% of NDs modified group. In TriplexHot material, significant differences were observed among all the groups, except between the control and the denture base material modified with 1.00wt% NDs (table 3).

Impact strength

The control groups demonstrated the highest mean impact strength among all the denture base materials. A decrease in impact strength was observed as the concentrations of NDs were increased in the denture base materials (table 1). One-way ANOVA showed significant differences in the impact strength within the denture base materials (table 1).

In post hoc analysis, Trevlon and TriplexHot denture base materials incorporated with 2.00wt% NDs showed significant differences with the control group and 0.50wt% NDs modified groups. The control group of DPI material exhibited significant differences with 1.00wt% and 2.00wt% of NDs groups (table 3).

Microhardness

The maximum microhardness was found in denture base materials containing 2.00wt% NDs, which is indirectly proportional to the increase in ND concentrations in the denture base materials (table 1). One-way ANOVA showed significant differences ($p=0.001$) between various concentrations of NDs incorporated in each denture base material (Table 1).

In post hoc analysis, significant differences ($p=0.001$) were observed between the control and modified groups of all three denture base materials. Among the modified groups, the Trevlon material modified with 0.50wt% NDs showed significant differences with 1.00wt% and 2.00wt% NDs modified groups (table 3). In the case of TriplexHot and DPI materials, significant differences were observed between 0.50wt% and 2.00wt% ND modified groups (table 3).

Water sorption and solubility

The least water sorption and solubility were observed in the unmodified specimens of all the denture base materials. Both the sorption and solubility were increased with an increase in the

Table 2: Water sorption and solubility of denture base resin materials incorporated with various concentrations of nanodiamonds

Material	Concentration of Nanodiamonds	N	Water sorption ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mm}^3$)		Water solubility ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mm}^3$)	
			Mean ± SD	p	Mean ± SD	p
Trevlon	0.00%	10	9.54 ± 1.03	0.001	0.68 ± 0.107	0.009
	0.50%	10	11.07 ± 1.06		0.71 ± 0.14	
	1.00%	10	13.17 ± 2.14		0.74 ± 0.07	
	2.00%	10	15.89 ± 1.54		0.78 ± 0.07	
TriplexHot	0.00%	10	8.60 ± 1.17	0.001	0.57 ± 0.14	0.148
	0.50%	10	13.14 ± 1.80		0.63 ± 0.04	
	1.00%	10	14.65 ± 1.43		0.67 ± 0.08	
	2.00%	10	16.42 ± 2.02		0.72 ± 0.08	
DPI	0.00%	10	9.76 ± 1.022	0.001	0.55 ± 0.081	0.009
	0.50%	10	11.27 ± 1.76		0.66 ± 0.16	
	1.00%	10	13.63 ± 2.21		0.71 ± 0.13	
	2.00%	10	16.15 ± 2.03		0.75 ± 0.12	

Table 3: Posthoc analysis of Flexural Strength, Impact strength and Vickers hardness of three denture base materials incorporated with various concentrations of nanodiamonds

Material	Concentrations of Nanodiamonds		Flexural Strength (MPa)		Impact Strength (KJ/mm ²)		Surface Hardness (Kg/mm ²)	
			Mean ± SE	p	Mean ± SE	p	Mean ± SE	p
Trevlon	Control	0.50%	15.36 ± 3.40	0.001	0.182 ± 0.12	0.407	6.474 ± 0.54	0.001
		1.00%	4.30 ± 3.40	0.591	0.305 ± 0.12	0.057	8.117 ± 0.54	0.001
		2.00%	12.40 ± 3.40	0.004	0.548 ± 0.12	0.000	9.456 ± 0.54	0.001
	0.50%	1.00%	19.66 ± 3.40	0.001	0.123 ± 0.12	0.714	1.643 ± 0.54	0.023
		2.00%	27.77 ± 3.40	0.001	0.366 ± 0.12	0.016	2.982 ± 0.54	0.001
		1.00%	2.00%	8.11 ± 3.40	0.098	0.243 ± 0.12	0.173	1.339 ± 0.54
TriplexHot	Control	0.50%	8.41 ± 2.68	0.017	0.089 ± 0.12	0.875	5.088 ± 0.70	0.001
		1.00%	3.64 ± 2.68	0.533	0.295 ± 0.12	0.080	6.463 ± 0.70	0.001
		2.00%	10.93 ± 2.68	0.001	0.489 ± 0.12	0.001	7.151 ± 0.70	0.001
	0.50%	1.00%	12.05 ± 2.68	0.001	0.206 ± 0.12	0.325	1.375 ± 0.70	0.225
		2.00%	19.33 ± 2.68	0.001	0.399 ± 0.12	0.010	2.063 ± 0.70	0.029
		1.00%	2.00%	7.28 ± 2.68	0.047	0.194 ± 0.12	0.377	0.688 ± 0.70
DPI	Control	0.50%	11.60 ± 3.106	0.003	0.239 ± 0.11	0.139	3.445 ± 0.85	0.001
		1.00%	3.76 ± 3.106	0.624	0.337 ± 0.11	0.017	5.150 ± 0.85	0.001
		2.00%	10.84 ± 3.106	0.007	0.517 ± 0.11	0.001	7.351 ± 0.85	0.001
	0.50%	1.00%	15.36 ± 3.106	0.001	0.099 ± 0.11	0.795	1.705 ± 0.85	0.205
		2.00%	22.44 ± 3.106	0.000	0.279 ± 0.11	0.063	3.906 ± 0.85	0.000
		1.00%	2.00%	7.083 ± 3.106	0.122	0.180 ± 0.11	0.354	2.201 ± 0.85

concentrations of NDs among the modified groups (table 2). One-way ANOVA showed significant differences in the sorption and solubilities among the various concentrations of denture base materials, except within the TriplexHot group in solubility (table 2).

In post hoc analysis, Significant differences were observed in the water sorption between unmodified and modified groups of TriplexHot denture base material. Whereas in the Trevlon and DPI materials, the control group exhibited significant differences with 1.00wt% and 2.00wt% of modified groups. Among the modified groups, 2.00wt% incorporation NDs showed significant differences

with 0.50wt% and 1.00wt% groups in Trevlon and DPI materials, and with 0.50wt% group in TriplexHot material (table 4). In water solubility, the unmodified group exhibited a significant difference with 2.00wt% of modified groups and no significant differences were observed between the modified groups the denture base material (table 4).

Discussion

PMMA based resin, is currently the most used material for the fabrication of removable denture prostheses. The forces of mastication induce stresses into the denture base and may generate

Table 4: Posthoc analysis of water sorption and solubility of denture base materials incorporated with various concentrations of nanodiamonds

Material	Concentrations of Nanodiamonds		Water sorption (µg/mm ³)		Water solubility (µg/mm ³)	
			Mean ± SE	p	Mean ± SE	p
Trevlon	Control	0.50%	01.53 ± 0.677	0.127	0.037 ± 0.046	0.087
		1.00%	3.62 ± 0.677	0.000	0.07 ± 0.046	0.054
		2.00%	6.34 ± 0.677	0.000	0.104 ± 0.046	0.019
	0.50%	1.00%	2.09 ± 0.677	0.019	0.032 ± 0.046	0.091
		2.00%	4.81 ± 0.677	0.000	0.067 ± 0.046	0.056
		1.00%	2.00%	2.72 ± 0.677	0.002	0.035 ± 0.046
TriplexHot	Control	0.50%	4.55 ± 0.73	0.000	0.062 ± 0.042	0.473
		1.00%	6.05 ± 0.73	0.000	0.101 ± 0.042	0.102
		2.00%	7.82 ± 0.73	0.000	0.151 ± 0.042	0.006
	0.50%	1.00%	1.50 ± 0.73	0.188	0.038 ± 0.042	0.801
		2.00%	3.27 ± 0.73	0.000	0.088 ± 0.042	0.179
		1.00%	2.00%	1.77 ± 0.73	0.091	0.050 ± 0.042
DPI	Control	0.50%	1.50 ± 0.81	0.264	0.106 ± 0.58	0.282
		1.00%	3.87 ± 0.81	0.000	0.156 ± 0.58	0.052
		2.00%	6.39 ± 0.81	0.000	0.203 ± 0.58	0.007
	0.50%	1.00%	2.36 ± 0.81	0.030	0.05 ± 0.58	0.828
		2.00%	4.88 ± 0.81	0.000	0.09 ± 0.58	0.358
		1.00%	2.00%	2.52 ± 0.81	0.018	0.047 ± 0.58

microcracks, resulting in denture prosthesis failure in the oral cavity [25-27]. Numerous studies attempted to reinforce the denture bases with different fillers including metal wires, various fibers, nanoparticles, and nanotubes. However, none of the reinforcements improved the overall mechanical properties of denture bases. Nanodiamonds are high-performance carbon-based materials with excellent physical and mechanical characteristics [19,20]. The applications of nanodiamonds have not been extensively investigated. Hence, this study was essentially designed to evaluate the effect of NDs incorporation on the physical and mechanical properties of some of the commonly used heat cure acrylic resins.

In the oral cavity, the denture prosthesis is largely subjected to the combination of compressive, tensile, and bending stresses under mastication. Therefore, it is ideal to characterize them using 3-point or four-point bending stresses. In the present study, the specimens were subjected to a 3-point bending stress to evaluate the flexural strength. It was observed that the denture base materials modified with 0.50wt% of NDs exhibited more flexural strength compared to unmodified materials. This can be attributed to the presence of a highly crystalline structure of NDs in the resin matrix [23]. In addition, the flexural strength of denture base specimens is also dependent on the size and dispersion of nanoparticles (NPs) in the resin matrix [23,28]. The size of the NDs (average particle size is 6 nm) used in the present study was much lesser than the polymer powder beads (around 100 μ m), resulted in occupying the interstitial spaces between the polymer chains and prevented the displacement of polymer chains under stresses [28]. Protopapa P *et al.* (2011) suggested that the nano-sized Diamonds interact adequately with the reactive functional groups that are present in the polymer matrix [29].

This study demonstrated a reduction in the flexural strength as the concentration of NDs was increased. Numerous studies reported that the nanoparticles tend to agglomerate as their concentration is increased in the resin matrix [28,30-32]. These agglomerations form voids at the interface of the NDs and polymer chains. These voids act as stress concentrations and propagate the cracks under masticatory loads [28]. In the present study, the decrease in flexural strength with an increase in the NDs concentration can be attributed to the agglomeration of NDs at 1.00wt% and 2.00wt%. The increase in flexural strength at 0.50wt% of NDs incorporation can be attributed to the uniform dispersion of NDs in the resin matrix [28]. Further, the agglomerated NDs are unable to bind as effectively as they were in nano size, with the reactive groups of the polymer matrix [23,29]. The results of the present study agreed with the study conducted by Fahad Al-Harbi *et al.* [23]. They also observed higher flexural strength with the incorporation of 0.50wt% of NDs and reported a decrease in flexural strength as their concentration increased greater than 0.50wt% in the PMMA matrix.

The resistance to impact forces also influences the performance of the denture prostheses. In this study, a significant decrease in the flexural strength was observed in the modified groups compared to the unmodified. A constant decrease in impact strength was observed with increased concentration of NDs among all the denture base materials. This indicates that the ND-modified denture prosthesis is unable to resist the impact forces. The decrease in impact strength can be attributed to the agglomeration of the NDs resulting in the formation of voids at the interfaces of the polymer and NDs [30-32]. Similar to the present study, Fahad Al-Harbi *et al.* (2018) also observed a decrease in the impact strength among the ND-modified PMMA resins. On the contrary, Protopapa *et al.* (2011) reported an increase in the impact strength of the PMMA resin used for fixed interim prostheses by reinforcing them with NDs [29]. However, the concentrations of NDs used in their study were different from the present study.

The surface hardness is also an important property along with the mechanical strength. Numerous studies have found that denture prostheses are prone to abrasion during conventional cleaning procedures due to their poor resistance to wear. This wearing results in the formation of surface roughness causing accumulation of plaque, and the denture becomes unhygienic [33,34]. Hence, this study was also focused to evaluate and compare the surface hardness of the heat-cure acrylics modified with various concentrations of NDs. In this study, unmodified acrylic specimens exhibited the least Vickers' hardness. Among the modified groups, the surface hardness was increased with an increase in the concentration of NDs. At specific concentrations of NDs incorporation, TriplexHot displayed slightly higher hardness than other denture base materials. The presence of hard nanofillers used in the study increased the hardness of modified acrylic specimens. Diamond is regarded as the world's hardest substance. In addition, the agglomerated NDs produce a thick immobilized PMMA matrix that resists indentation. This behavior was demonstrated in this work, where the hardness of the polymer enhanced as the concentration of NDs in the polymer increased [34]. The findings of this investigation were consistent with earlier research, however, the type of nanofillers was different from the present study [34]. The types of nanofillers used in this investigation, however, are distinct from those used in previous studies.

Denture base polymers tend to absorb water over time due to the polar characteristics of the resin molecules. The absorbed water may serve as a plasticizer and reduces the prosthesis strength [35,36]. Water sorption also alters the dimensional stability of the denture prosthesis, causing it to misfit in the mouth [35-37]. In this study, the unmodified denture base materials showed the least water sorption and solubility and when the concentration of NDs in the resin matrix increased in the modified specimens, the water sorption and solubility were increased. Water sorption is mostly caused by the leaching of water-soluble compounds such as plasticizers into the water, and these sites will eventually be occupied by water. Furthermore, the aggregation of nanoparticles causes voids to appear in the polymer matrix, allowing more water to be absorbed. The soluble components present in acrylic resins include initiators, plasticizers, and free monomers. Various studies suggested that there is a correlation between residual monomer and the weight loss determined by the solubility tests [36]. The denture base specimens used in this study exhibited the least solubility in water.

The ND concentrations employed in this study were 0.50wt%, 1.00wt %, and 2.00wt%. A change in the color of the specimens was observed at all the concentrations that necessitate the usage of NDs in non-esthetic areas, only. The present study investigated all the properties under dry conditions, which does not simulate the oral situations. Therefore, future research may focus on lowering the NDs concentration, their dispersion in the resin matrix, and evaluating the properties in oral conditions.

Conclusion

In the present study, the denture base materials modified with 0.50wt% of NDs demonstrated superior flexural strength. The flexural and impact strengths of the ND modified acrylic specimens, on the other hand, decreased as their concentrations increased. The concentration of NDs in all the denture base materials assessed was found to have a direct correlation with surface hardness. The ND-modified denture base materials showed a negligible increase in water sorption and solubility compared to unmodified materials.

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